

FACTORS INFLUENCING STUDENTS LEVEL OF PREPAREDNESS - A PARADIGM SHIFT FROM DISCIPLINE SPECIFIC TO TRANS DISCIPLINARY STUDIES

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Abstract :

Presently in case of Higher Education, there are specific disciplines. However, in the near future, on the sanction of National Education Policy and its implementation there would be a paradigm shift from discipline specific to trans-disciplinary studies. Such an education system throws open lots of opportunities for the younger generation from specific stream based education system to a choice based graduation system. Rather than selecting one stream for graduation, this system proposes trans-disciplinary options based on their strengths and weaknesses. The major focus of the entire policy is on the students' and naturally the students play a pivotal role in the success of this dream project. Every coin has two sides, though many good things are proposed in the Plan document, the consideration of students' mindset for the transition holds highest weightage. This paper makes an attempt to study the physical, psychological, economic factors influencing the level of preparedness of the students that would affect this transition. The study consists of primary and secondary data. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection. Null hypotheses were tested using Mann-Whitney U test and Kruskal Wallis test. This study will help understand the different factors affecting student preparedness for accepting the shift from discipline specific to trans-disciplinary studies.

Key words: *#Acceptingthechange#Changeineducation, #TransdisciplinaryApproach, #Paradigm, #Studentspreparedness #Factorsforchange #Physicalfactors #Psychologicalfactors #Economicalfactors*

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Introduction :

The paradigm shift from specific stream to trans-disciplinary options to students at all levels by National Education Policy sounds interesting as well as challenging. No doubt, this proposed education system throws open lots of opportunities for the younger generation by introducing them to choice based graduation system. The preparation of this educational reform begins at the preliminary level itself and many reforms are expected at different levels. Whilst the Macaulay system practiced currently emphasizes on rote-learning, the proposed policy suggests conceptual learning. The proposal of pre-primary education in local/ regional language or mother-tongue is an added advantage

for many students especially in rural India and even those who have moved to urban areas get a chance to get connected to the roots. The next level proposes multi-disciplinary option to choose subjects based on personal interest or inclination towards the same. This boosts the creativity amongst the students and breaks the boundaries laid down by specific stream based education.

The critical thinking capacity to make logical decisions and encourage innovations is one of the prime motives of this policy. It also promotes ethical, humanity and constitutional values to be imbibed among every student. A holistic approach is being incorporated in this policy for overall development of the student as a whole. This would ensure the final product is rich in values and strong with values to face life with smiling face forever. In the midst of academic importance, due care is given regarding developing basic skills. All facets of life like academics, sports, culture, arts are opened up for every student to get involved and emerge victorious in life. The different authorities controlling the different areas are amalgamated into a single window which eases out the pains from students point of view.

Though enormous thought process has been put into preparation of this policy with a view of imparting skill based education system which would generate employment opportunities adding an essence of the traditional value based educational system, the ground level implementation would decide the success of the dream project in the educational sector.

The major focus of the entire policy is on the students' exposure. Naturally, the students play a pivotal role in the success of this dream project. Every coin has two sides, though many good things are proposed in the Plan document, the consideration of students' mindset for the transition holds highest weightage. This paper makes an attempt to study the various factors which would affect this transition.

Review of Literature :

1. Through his paper, "New Education Policy (NEP) 2020: A Roadmap for India 2.0", Mr. Alok Kumar, School of Commerce, Jain (Deemed University), India published in Glocers 21, Volume 4, the author concludes that the New Education Policy, NEP 2020 is largely a very progressive document, with a firm grasp on the current socio-economic landscape and the prospect to meet future challenges. He further adds a disclaimer that no policy bears any fruit if that is not implemented in an appropriate way. However, as per his personal opinion the given policy is well thought and genuine attempt to remodel Indian Educational system. He feels that the policy highlights the integration of professional education in HEI for skilling and employment generation. His final conclusion is that the NEP 2020 has laid a concrete roadmap for India 2.0 and if implemented properly; it has got everything to make India global hub in education by 2030.
2. Through his paper, "An Empirical Study on NEP 2020 [National Education Policy] with Special Reference to the Future of Indian Education System and Its effects on the Stakeholders", KalyaniPawan concludes that The education system has shifted the focus from learn what the system want to provide to learn what the students wants to learn according to their choice and preferences. He also infers that the execution of the policy will define the success of this policy.

- Through the article, “A student’s perspective on the New Education Policy, 2020” published in Times of India on September 11, 2020, Ms. Arundati Menon highlighted on the various positives and negatives related to NEP 2020. As a student of Std 12th, the concept of multi-disciplinary options at the Undergraduate level is a point of attraction for the student community. On the other hand, the role of HECL (the centralized authority) is not clear along with protection of intellectual freedom and autonomy of colleges and students has not been addressed by the policy, concludes the young girl.

Significance of the study :

The experts in the field of education have drafted a wonderful policy combining various factors past and present to make the future of our country - independent, skillful and dynamic. The entire onus of success of this policy though depends on the perception of students. Therefore, this paper is an attempt to study the various factors affecting the preparedness of the students due to the paradigm from existing system to the trans-disciplinary system. This study would be an eye-opener for the makers of the policy with respect to the variance in the thought process of the two ends of the policy – policy makers and the students.

Objectives of the Study :

- To study the concept of specific stream to trans-disciplinary stream approach in the Higher Education of the National Education Policy, 2020.
- To study the awareness amongst the students regarding to trans-disciplinary studies in Higher Education of the NEP 2020.
- To analyse theselected factor affecting students preparedness with regards to paradigm shift from discipline specific to trans-disciplinary studies of NEP 2020.

Hypotheses:

- H_0 - There is no significant difference between Gender and factors affecting preparedness of students.
 H_1 – There is a significant difference between Gender and factors affecting preparedness of students.
- H_0 - There is no significant difference between Class and factors affecting preparedness of students.
 H_1 – There is a significant difference between Class and factors affecting preparedness of students regarding NEP 2020
- H_0 - There is no significant difference between Courses taken and factors affecting preparedness of students
 H_1 – There is a significant difference between Courses taken and factors affecting preparedness of students.

Limitations of Study :

- The area is restricted to students of Commerce Faculty.
- There was a time constraint to meet more Students for collection of data.

Research Methodology :

The research study is indicative and analytical in nature. Both primary and secondary data was collected. Primary data was collected by floating structured questionnaire through Google forms among students. The questionnaire was framed with seven-point Likert scale. The secondary data was collected from books, articles & Research Paper and websites. The population for the study was degree college students, primarily belonging to Commerce faculty. The Convenient Sampling Method was used. After the responses were received, it was classified, tabulated and summarized and gets covered in the flow of paper.

Data Analysis :

The data analysis was done by using SPSS package. The normality test was conducted to check normality of data by using Kolmogorov-Smirnov & Shapiro-Wilk test. The data was found to be Non Normal therefore null hypotheses were tested by using Non parametric tests i.eMann-Whitney U test and Kruskal Wallis test.

Normality Testing :

Normality was conducted for the data using Kolmogorov-Smirnov & Shapiro-Wilk test.

H_0 : Distribution is Normal

H_1 : Distribution is Non-Normal

**Table 1
Tests of Normality**

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Preparedness of students towards the paradigm shift from discipline specific to trans-disciplinary studies	.075	118	.003	.975	118	.002

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Source: Primary data

The table 1 indicated significant value for the variable was less than 0.05 which means the Null Hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted that is distribution is non-Normal hence appropriate non-Parametric test Mann-Whitney U test and Kruskal Wallis test were used for further analysis.

Testing of Hypotheses :

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Gender and factors affecting preparedness of students.

H_1 : There is a significant difference between Gender and factors affecting preparedness of students.

Table 2

Mann-Whitney U Test – Gender and factors affecting preparedness of students

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
There is no significant difference between Gender and factors affecting preparedness of students.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.633	Retain the null hypothesis.

Source: Primary data

Table number 2 indicated that significant value is 0.633 which is greater than 0.05 thereby indicating the null hypothesis is accepted that means there is no significant difference between Gender and factors affecting preparedness of students.

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Class and factors affecting preparedness of students.

H_1 : There is no significant difference between Class and factors affecting preparedness of students.

Table 3

Kruskal Wallis Test – Class of students and factors affecting preparedness of students

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
There is no significant difference between Class and factors affecting preparedness of students.	Independent-Samples Kruskal Wallis Test	.838	Retain the null hypothesis.

Source: Primary data

Table number 3 indicated that significant value is 0.838 which is greater than 0.05 thereby indicating the null hypothesis is accepted that means there is no significant difference between class of students and factors affecting preparedness of students.

H_0 : There is no significant difference between Courses and factors affecting preparedness of students.

H_1 : There is a significant difference between Courses taken and factors affecting preparedness of students

Table 4

Kruskal Wallis Test –Courses Undertaken and factors affecting Preparedness of Students

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
There is no significant difference between Course and factors affecting preparedness of students	Independent-Samples Kruskal Wallis Test	.116	Retain the null hypothesis.

Source: Primary data

Table number 4 indicated that significant value is 0.116 which is greater than 0.05 thereby indicating the null hypothesis is accepted that means there is no significant difference between Course undertaken and factors affecting preparedness of students.

Findings:

1. Of the total respondents, 44.1% were male while 55.9% were female.
2. The first year students were 50.8%, second year student were 20.3% and 23.8% were third year students.
3. Students of B.Com were 61%, BAF were 22%, BMS were 13.6% and 3.4% were BBI.
4. Majority of the students (85.6%) were aware that National Education Policy, 2020 would promote creativity. 11.9% were neutral on their opinion and 2.5% disagreed to this fact.
5. 77.1% of all the students were aware about educational reforms. 16.1% of the students were neutral and 6.8% disagreed with this mentioned fact.
6. As far as preparedness of the students is concerned, the Gender, Grades or Courses undertaken were in alignment and no significant difference was observed in their opinions.

Suggestions:

1. A high level of awareness about the policy in Higher Education will help their preparedness for facing the transition issues.
2. Appointment of 'Counselor' for every need of the student right from the pre-primary stage up to the graduation level.
3. The parents, teachers and organisations must take the onus on themselves and organize workshops regularly for creating awareness about NEP and the opportunities opened up by this newer policy must be put forth to the students in the most simplest way.
4. Every factor that will help improve students' preparedness like the Psychological factors, Physical factors as well as economic factors must be provided to them in the best possible manner. The use of social media for urban students and conduct of workshops and webinars for semi-urban and rural area students must be given an in-depth-thought.
5. Simplicity must be highlighted for better preparedness of students overall acceptance and success of the policy.
6. This policy in general and the implementation part with Higher Education in particular with reference to multidisciplinary/trans-disciplinary facilities offered to the students can be simplified.
7. Teachers must be made aware about the change to happen soon. Workshops for teachers to help them understand the implementation part of the discipline specific to trans-disciplinary courses offered at each program.
8. There must be institutionalization of the National Education Policy, 2020 for better implementation. Institutionalization, per se, would mean awareness and factual information from top to bottom of the pyramid.

If it is this way, then it will be percolate to the bottom of the pyramid in the correct sense

Discussion:

This is only one aspect of one level of the pyramid. The Physical, Psychological, Economic factors were taken together. Further, number of studies can be conducted on these factors separately. Also additional factors like socio-cultural, behavioural, demographic and international factors can be considered for conducting a 360 degree analysis research giving due weightage to different stakeholders in this paradigm shift.

Conclusion:

The boundaries of stream based education are on the verge of being broken to offer better avenues for students to explore and experiment with their career. However, the same freedom can become a trap of confusion if not explained properly. It is easier to walk the path treaded than tread a self-path of realisation. The current mindset of students has been trained to take instructions and follow the same to achieve success. However, the NEP 2020 expects them to introspect, identify their strength and weakness and capitalize on their strengths to build their own career. This aspect of opening up of various avenues simultaneously may create a lot of confusion in the young minds. The students carry along the burden of expectations of everyone around and the transition from the current system to trans-disciplinary system will be added responsibility. Regular workshops and counseling lectures will empower them to break the shell and enjoy the benefits of education showered upon them. This policy is a breakthrough educational reform without a doubt. The students though will play a pivotal role in determining the success of this policy. However, the different factors preparing them to tread this uphill task needs to be analysed properly and negated carefully with optimum care. Hence, all the factors which determine the preparedness for acceptance of the policy must be given due importance. It is beyond doubt that the next generation are expected to reap the benefit of seeds sown by the current generation of academic stakeholders (students, teachers, parents, society).

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